

GROWTH OF RICE PRODUCTION IN INDIA

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Abstract

The study was conducted to analyze the growth rate and instability of rice production in major rice producing states of India. For the purpose of study secondary data on area, production and productivity of rice was collected from the official website of Indiatat.com. The study was conducted for a period from 2000-01 to 2020-21. The analytical tools used in the study were simple growth rate and instability index. The findings of the study showed that growth rate of area was negative for most of the states except for Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. But on the contrary growth rate of production and productivity was positive throughout the study period for all the states as well as for India. Madhya Pradesh showed highest growth rate in area, production as well as in productivity among all the states. Andhra Pradesh showed highest instability in area among all states while for production and productivity highest instability was observed for Tamil Nadu during the study period. This clearly indicating that traditionally non rice growing state like Madhya Pradesh is emerging as the major rice growing state.

Keywords: Simple growth rate, Area, Production, Productivity, Instability index

Introduction

Rice is among one of the most crucial foodgrains not only in India but globally. Rice first originated in East Asia over 10,000 years ago, it was domesticated and widely grown throughout Asia and later, it was made known to the rest of the world. Rice is a staple food in many parts of Asia due to its ability to grow in a variety of climates and soil types. It is also a very versatile crop that can be used in a wide range of dishes. Additionally, rice is a good source of carbohydrates and other nutrients, including protein, fibre, and various vitamins and minerals. As a result, it is an important source of energy and nutrition for many people in Asia. Rice has been a staple food in Asia for thousands of years, and it has become deeply ingrained in the region's culture and cuisine. Many traditional dishes in Asia are based around rice, and it is often served in large quantities at meals. Rice grows best in warm and humid conditions, which are prevalent in many parts of Asia. The topography of the region, including many river deltas, also provides ideal growing conditions for rice. Rice is an affordable and accessible crop in Asia, making it a popular choice for farmers and consumers alike. It is also easy to store and transport, which makes it a reliable source of food throughout the year.

Almost 85 per cent of the rice produced in the world is produced mainly by just ten countries. More than half of all production worldwide is produced by the top two countries. China and India producing 28 (211.4 million tons) and 23.5 per cent (177.6 million tons) of total rice production in the world (2019) as per the data from the UN's FAOSTAT and the USDA. After China and India, Indonesia and Bangladesh contribute to 7.2 per cent of global rice production with 54.6 million tons of global rice production followed by Vietnam and Thailand with 5.7 per cent (43.4 million tons) and 3.7 per cent (28.3 million tons) share in total rice production during the year 2019, respectively (Wallach, 2022). According to the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare, in India area under rice cultivation has increased from 43.8 million hectares in 2000-01 to 44.9 million hectares in 2020-21, while production increased from 93.8 million tonnes to 118.9 million tonnes during the same period. Rice had a share of 35.26 per cent in area and 40.02 per cent in total foodgrain production in India (2020-21). Rice is also one of the most significant Indian agricultural products for export. Rice exports from India have increased as a result of the consistent rise in production, the availability of buffer stock, and the rising demand for basmati rice on the global market (Adhikari et al., 2016). India is also a major exporter of rice exporting around 14.37 million tonnes of rice (2020-21), according to the Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA). Millions of small farmers and people in poverty choose rice not just as a source of livelihood

but also for household food security (Nain et al., 2019). Many states of India contribute significantly in rice production which includes West Bengal which is the largest producer of rice with 15 per cent of total rice production, Uttar Pradesh is the second-largest producer of rice in India, with around 14 per cent of the total rice production, Punjab with 12 per cent of total rice production, Andhra Pradesh (10%), Tamil Nadu (7%), Bihar (6%) etc.

There are several policies and programs in India related to rice production and procurement which include minimum support price (MSP) which aims to ensure fair price for produce and to incentivize them to grow more rice, National Food Security Mission (NFSM), launched in 2007 to provide financial and technical assistance to farmers to adopt improved technologies and practices for rice cultivation, Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) which is a crop insurance scheme launched in 2016 to provide financial support to farmers in case of crop losses due to natural calamities, pests, and diseases, Electronic National Agriculture Market (eNAM) is an electronic trading platform launched in 2016 to create a unified national market for agricultural commodities, including rice aiming to promote transparency and efficiency in the trading of agricultural produce and to help farmers get better prices for their crops. Similarly National Rice Development Program (NRDP) is a centrally-sponsored scheme launched in 2011 to promote rice production and productivity in the country by providing financial assistance to states for activities such as seed production, extension services, and research and development. Keeping in view the importance of rice in national food security present study was undertaken to analyse the growth and instability of production in major rice producing states of India.

Methodology

The study is based on secondary data on area, production and productivity of rice which were obtained from the official website of Indiatat.com (<https://www.indiatat.com/>). The study was confined for a period of 21 years (2000-01 to 2020-21). For the analysis purpose major rice producing states of India were selected. The states considered for the study include Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal which collectively accounted for approximately 80 per cent of total area and 79 per cent of the total rice production in India. The remaining states were pooled as 'others'. The various analytical tools used in the study included:

Net change: - Net change is an approach of comparing changes over time in area/production/productivity of crop. For study average of area, production, and productivity for the base year (TE for 2000-01 to 2002-3) and the average of the current year (TE for 2018-19 to

2020–2021) of the study period were used to calculate the net change in area, production, and productivity (Singh et.al,2014).

Net change= $Y_n - Y_o$

Where,

Y_n = Current year value of area/ production/ productivity (TE for 2018-19 to 2020–2021)

Y_o = Base year value of area/ production/ productivity (TE for 2000-01 to 2002-3)

Percentage change- This method was used to measure the comparative change in area, production and productivity of rice in various states of India over the period of time by using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage change} = \frac{Y_n - Y_o}{Y_o} \times 100$$

Where,

Y_n and Y_o have the same notations as stated above

Simple growth rate- Simple growth rate (SGR) was used in the study to estimate the growth of area, production and productivity of rice in various states over the period using the following formula:

$$\text{SGR} = \frac{b}{\text{mean}} \times 100$$

Where,

b = regression coefficient

Instability index-Instability in area, production and productivity of rice was measured by using the instability index developed by Ray (1983) which is as follow:

Instability index= Standard deviation of natural logarithm (Y_{t+1}/Y_t)

Where,

Y_t is the area / production/ productivity in the current year &

Y_{t+1} is the area / production/ productivity in the next year

Results

The collected data were analysed to get a clear picture of growth and instability of rice production in India. The data on absolute and relative change in rice production in different states of India is given in table 1. It was observed that in absolute and relative terms the area under rice declined in all the states over the period except for Andhra

Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh and Punjab. In relative terms highest decline in area of rice was noted for the state of Bihar (-16 %) and it was increased in highest terms in the state of Andhra Pradesh (including the Telangana) with relative change of 32.50 per cent. For the country as a whole the increase in area under rice was only 2.13 per cent during last two decades. It was declined marginally in the state of Assam (-8.39%), Chhattisgarh (-2.59%), Odisha (-10.36%), Uttar Pradesh (-0.16%), West Bengal (-4.37). The percentage share of area under rice to total area of the country was increased for Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, and Punjab. This shows that these three states are emerging as major rice growing states in India for the enhancing the production under rice. Marginal increase in percentage share of area under rice was observed for Tamil Nadu and other states.

In production of rice the highest relative change was noted for Madhya Pradesh (269.25%) with absolute change of 33.27 lakh tons during last two decades and this is followed by Chhattisgarh (10.05%) with absolute increase of 34.62 lakh tons. Thus, these two states of central India are presently contributing around 10 per cent of the total rice production of the country. The share of production of rice to total production in the country was declined for the states of West Bengal and Tamil Nadu and for remaining states it was more or less stable. In absolute terms Andhra Pradesh contributed with highest net gain in production with 59.72 lakh tons followed by Uttar Pradesh with about 41.51 lakh tons and other states with 73.05 lakh tons.

The results of net and percentage changes in productivity of rice showed that over the years there was increase in productivity of rice in various states and also for India. Over the study period, highest net change was observed by Madhya Pradesh with 1397.67Kg/ha followed by other states with net change of 1343.41 Kg/ha, followed by Odisha (971.71 Kg/ha), whereas West Bengal showed the lowest net change with 516 kg/ha. Highest percentage change was observed by Madhya Pradesh with 195.75 per cent followed by Chhattisgarh with 108.69 per cent. In India percentage change of 41.13 per cent was observed for the productivity of rice.

Table 1: Change and share in area (000'ha), production (000'tons) and productivity (kg/ha) of rice in major rice producing states of India (2000-01 to 2020-21)

States	Particular	Base year	Percent share	Current year	Percent share	Net change	% change
Andhra Pradesh*	Area	3630.03	8.33	4809.83	10.80	1179.80	32.50
	Production	10391.60	12.46	16363.77	13.65	5972.17	57.47
	Productivity	2836.71	148.70	3453.06	128.26	616.35	21.73
Assam	Area	2575.77	5.91	2358.72	5.30	-216.04	-8.39
	Production	3863.50	4.63	5140.00	4.29	1276.50	33.04
	Productivity	1500.33	78.65	2179.33	80.95	679.00	45.26
Bihar	Area	3597.77	8.25	3022.33	6.79	-575.44	-15.99
	Production	5243.67	6.29	6400.16	5.34	1156.50	22.06
	Productivity	1458.67	76.41	2121.00	78.78	663.33	45.51
Chhattisgarh	Area	3785.80	8.68	3687.67	8.28	-98.13	-2.59
	Production	3359.30	4.03	6820.94	5.69	3461.64	103.05
	Productivity	886.00	46.44	1849.00	68.68	963.00	108.69
Madhya Pradesh	Area	1721.77	3.95	2174.67	4.88	452.90	26.30
	Production	1235.53	1.48	4562.23	3.80	3326.69	269.25
	Productivity	714.00	37.43	2111.67	78.43	1397.67	195.75
Odisha	Area	4402.33	10.10	3946.12	8.86	-456.21	-10.36
	Production	5012.90	6.01	8301.46	6.92	3288.56	65.60
	Productivity	1131.96	59.34	2102.67	78.10	971.71	85.75
Punjab	Area	2543.67	5.83	2984.67	6.70	441.00	17.34
	Production	8950.00	10.73	12461.51	10.39	3511.51	39.23
	Productivity	3520.22	184.53	4177.33	155.16	657.12	18.67
Uttar Pradesh	Area	5730.40	13.14	5721.00	12.85	-9.40	-0.16
	Production	11376.70	13.64	15527.70	12.95	4151.00	36.49
	Productivity	1978.43	103.71	2714.00	100.80	735.57	37.18

West Bengal	Area	5782.13	13.26	5530.73	12.42	-252.41	-4.37
	Production	14024.67	16.82	16216.03	13.52	2191.36	15.63
	Productivity	2421.15	126.92	2936.67	109.08	515.52	21.29
Tamil Nadu	Area	1887.83	4.33	1888.30	4.24	1.47	0.08
	Production	5842.47	7.01	6728.74	5.61	885.28	15.15
	Productivity	3030.00	158.83	3567.00	132.49	537.00	17.72
Others	Area	5401.50	12.39	5423.44	12.18	21.94	0.41
	Production	14078.87	16.89	21383.94	17.83	7305.07	51.89
	Productivity	2602.24	136.41	3945.65	146.55	1343.41	51.63
India	Area	43598.67	100.00	44529.14	100.00	930.48	2.13
	Production	83379.20	100.00	119905.49	100.00	36526.29	43.81
	Productivity	1907.67	100.00	2692.33	100.00	784.67	41.13

Base year= Average of triennium ending between 2000-01 to 2002-03

Current year=Average of triennium ending between 2018-19 to 2020-21

*Andhra Pradesh including Telangana

Table 2: Instability in area, production and productivity of Rice in major rice producing states of India (2000-01 to 2020-21)

State	Area	Production	Productivity
Andhra Pradesh*	26.20	26.19	18.76
Assam	21.67	9.33	19.94
Bihar	25.01	32.29	27.36
Chhattisgarh	1.66	34.44	33.94
Madhya Pradesh	9.45	27.22	24.22
Odisha	2.98	30.31	28.26
Punjab	2.81	5.73	4.20
Uttar Pradesh	7.21	15.57	10.10
West Bengal	5.46	6.83	3.17
Tamil Nadu	21.08	44.48	39.27
Others	18.69	12.91	18.77
India	74.28	9.25	6.62

*Andhra Pradesh including Telangana

Data for instability is presented in table 2, the findings showed that area under rice in Andhra Pradesh observed highest instability with 26.20 per cent followed by Bihar with 25.01 per cent while least instability in area was observed by Chhattisgarh state with 1.66 per cent. In production of rice, Tamil Nadu showed highest instability with 44.48 per cent followed by Chhattisgarh (34.44 %) and least instability in production was observed for Punjab (5.73 %). Highest instability for productivity of rice was observed for Tamil Nadu with 39.27 per cent followed by Chhattisgarh with 33.94 per cent, while lowest instability was observed for West Bengal (3.17 %).

Table 3: Simple growth rate in area, production and productivity of Rice in various states of India during period 2000-01 to 2020-21:

S.no.	State	Area (000'ha)		Production (000'tonnes)		Productivity (Kg/ha)	
		b (SE)	SGR (%)	b (SE)	SGR (%)	b (SE)	SGR (%)
1.	Andhra Pradesh*	30.83 (30.02)	0.85	203.98 (96.86)	1.73*	29.92 (18.30)	0.92
2.	Assam	-25.49 (17.91)	-1.00	98.56 (15.46)	2.25**	50.98 (6.74)	2.91**
3.	Bihar	-55.41 (28.69)	-1.60	152.32 (47.00)	2.72**	66.03 (12.66)	3.95**
4.	Chhattisgarh	-1.81 (2.11)	-0.05	170.30 (34.24)	3.11**	46.02 (8.80)	3.16**
5.	Madhya Pradesh	30.73 (6.33)	1.67**	195.81 (18.52)	7.79**	80.75 (6.70)	6.17**
6.	Odisha	-35.09 (4.66)	-0.83**	129.16 (36.70)	1.87**	44.87 (7.66)	2.72**
7.	Punjab	26.01 (2.37)	0.93**	184.27 (17.51)	1.69**	29.81 (5.23)	0.76**
8.	Uttar Pradesh	5.70 (9.29)	0.10	210.88 (45.73)	1.65**	34.96 (6.29)	1.58**
9.	West Bengal	-22.83 (8.16)	-0.41*	97.63 (26.46)	0.66**	28.61 (2.07)	1.07**
10.	Tamil Nadu	-13.67 (8.97)	-0.73	48.09 (51.97)	0.85	39.79 (23.64)	1.32
11.	Others	68.41 (32.85)	1.16	486.69 (77.68)	2.52**	46.31 (15.27)	1.40**
12.	India	2596.19	5.95	1921.73	1.92**	41.12	1.80**

		(3100.99)		(188.90)		(3.02)	
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**Significant at 1 per cent

*Significant at 5 per cent

*Andhra Pradesh including Telangana

Data in table 3 presents the simple growth rate in rice area, production and productivity in various states over the period 2000-01 to 2020-21. The data showed that for area negative growth rate was observed in most the states except for Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. Madhya Pradesh showed highest growth rate in area among the considered states with 1.67 per cent followed by other states with 1.16 per cent and Punjab (0.93 %). For India the growth rate for area was positive with 5.95 per cent. Highest growth rate of production was also observed for Madhya Pradesh with 7.79 per cent followed by Chhattisgarh with 3.11 per cent while lowest growth rate was observed for West Bengal with 0.66 per cent during the study period. For other states and India positive and significant growth rate of production of rice was observed with 2.52 and 1.92 per cent respectively. For productivity of rice, positive growth rate was observed in all the states. Highest growth rate of productivity of rice was observed in Madhya Pradesh with 6.17 per cent followed by Andhra Pradesh with 5.13 per cent, whereas Punjab recorded lowest growth rate with 0.76 per cent.

Conclusion

From the ongoing study it can be concluded that over the years area under rice declined in all the states except for Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab and Tamil Nadu whereas there was increase in production and productivity of rice over the period in all considered states as well as for India. Andhra Pradesh showed highest net and percentage change in area among all states. For production highest net change was observed by other states followed by Andhra Pradesh whereas Madhya Pradesh recorded highest percentage change in production. For productivity Madhya Pradesh showed highest net as well as percentage change among all the considered states. Area under rice showed negative growth rate for most of the considered states during the study period except for Andhra Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Punjab and Uttar Pradesh. Growth rate of production and productivity of rice was observed to be positive for all the states as

well as for India. Madhya Pradesh showed highest growth rate in area, production as well as in productivity of rice among all the states during the study period. Among the various states Andhra Pradesh showed highest instability in area while Tamil Nadu followed by Chhattisgarh showed highest instability for production as well as for productivity.

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